

Cryptography and Network Security of aBlockchain

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Abstract— In storing data to any of the server privacy and security over the network becomes the major concern to the consumers and developers. As data theft and data corruption are few major factors that are always in highlights of the data misuse. As security over network is given by encrypting the data and identity of the consumers by performing several substantial algorithms etc. In this paper we will do analysis of security measures, attacks and cryptography of the private and public blockchains and some of the privacy concerned to look after [3]. Most blockchain users remain open to privacy attacks. , To make sure access privacy, many any researchers advocate using anonymous communications networks, such as Tor We challenge this method, showing the need for mechanisms through which non-anonymous users can publish and fetch transactions without being others to link those transactions to their network addresses or to their other transactions [1].

Keywords— Cryptographic, Hashing, Permissioned, Permissionless, Ledger.

I INTRODUCTION

The security of the blockchain is regulated by factors such as distributed consensus, and incentive mechanism, data encryption, time stamping, rather than a TTP [3], other than this some cryptosystem algorithm such as DES, AES, SHA, Blowfish and other play diverse role in Blockchain. In future SDN (Software defined Network) could be used to perform security tracing and node failure detection in the future [2]. Blockchain, is a kind of distributed ledger that comes up a great deal of attention because of its wide range of application as Hyperledger, cryptocurrency, NFT, Healthcare sector, Supply chain management, etc. and its transparency, decentralization and unbending (immutability) [3]

II PUBLISHING TRANSACTIONS ANONYMOUSLY

Blockchain system require multiple networks through which users announce transactions to the nodes and agree on which transaction should be reflected to the blockchain. Thus, it seems natural to leverage the existing overlay structure to perceive anonymous transaction publishing, rather than depending on an external like Tor [3]. Initiate and deployed blockchains fall into two distinct categories based on the mechanism they use to construct a consensus around what data to commemorate in the blockchain [3].

III FETCHING TRANSACTION PRIVATELY

Unlike traditional databases, blockchains use cryptography to ensure decentralization and tamper resistance. However, users who hold a complete local model of the blockchain can enjoy these attributes, which is increasingly becoming impractical due to the blockchain's size. To address this, many users utilize thin clients that rely on Simplified Payment Verification (SPV) mode. SPV mode involves downloading block headers and verifying their validity, allowing thin clients to request transaction details without holding the entire blockchain. However, this approach raises privacy concerns, as naive implementation may expose thin clients' public addresses to full nodes, potentially leading to deanonymization and targeting of users for theft. The passage proposes solving this privacy issue using Private Information Retrieval (PIR), a cryptographic technique enabling clients to query a remote database while keeping queries and responses private. Although PIR techniques have historically been inefficient, recent advancements offer practical possibilities for implementing PIR-based solutions to protect users' privacy when fetching blockchain transactions. Despite the need for further research and engineering efforts, these advances hold the potential to address privacy concerns in blockchain transactions' retrieval effectively. [3]

IV PERMISSIONED BLOCKCHAIN

In the permissioned blockchain is regulated by the control layer that runs on the top of the blockchain, it requires access to be part of the network. Generally permissioned blockchain are to be the closed chain that is private and it is regulated within

certain range of nodes, it requires permission to participate in the nodes which makes it fit not making unnecessary transaction within the respective block, only permitted nodes can make a transaction in the respective block. This type of chains is used in business purpose, government sector, industrial sector, healthcare, Ripple (Recent permissioned blockchain) and Hyperledger. The nodes transaction is permitted by asynchronous Byzantine-tolerant consensus protocols to include a block of transactions to blockchain [1]. Proof of Work is takes up intensive energy in public blockchains, Proof of Authority or Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance are consensus mechanisms which provides faster transaction validation which are often used in permissioned blockchains

Fig. 1 Permissioned Blockchain

Fig. 1 shows how the permissioned blockchain, private blockchain works when a transaction is made by a person to another, there is a consortium layer in the middle that controls the transaction. In permissioned blockchains, it generally seen that the participants or user has the peak level of control and accountability over their blockchain network. This often includes the identity management system or digital identities, which are authenticated and verified by the central authority. This method enhances the security and regulatory compliance, as the identity of participants can be confirmed and verified before they gain access to the network. Moreover, permissioned blockchains enable fine-grained access controls, allowing participants to define who can read, write, and execute transactions within the network. This flexibility provides privileges to make permissioned blockchains a good option for consortia, consortiums, and private business networks that require secure, efficient, and regulated collaboration. By maintaining a controlled environment that prioritizes privacy, permissioned blockchains bridge the gap between the open and decentralized nature of public blockchains and the stringent requirements of enterprise-grade applications.

V PERMISSIONLESS BLOCKCHAIN

This is an open-source distributed network that can be accessed by any individual who wants to participate in the blockchain and wants to make transaction in the respective node. In permissionless blockchain, the ajar and transparency of the permissionless blockchain help improve its trust but the disclosure of transaction content sometimes leads to crucial privacy leaks, especially when it is applied in situations like Mobile Crowd Sourcing and the Internet of Things (IoT), in which transactions may contain sensitive information of users [3]. Ethereum allows participants to run smart contract on the blockchain, which expands the application of the blockchain.

Fig. 2 Permissionless Blockchain

Fig. 2 shows the working of the permissionless blockchain a public blockchain in which there is no middle layer and the transaction is committed to the open network in blockchain. But there is a drawback of using it, that if a person gain 51% or more computing power of a public blockchain network, they can singly alter it.

VI CRYPTOGRAPHIC HASHING AND ITS ROLE IN DATA SECURITY

Cryptographic hashing is a fundamental technique used to enhance data security and integrity. It involves transforming input data of arbitrary length into a fixed-size hash value, commonly represented as a string of characters. This hash value is computed using a specific algorithm and is irreversible, making it impossible to revert back to the original input. Cryptographic hashing plays a pivotal role in ensuring data remains unaltered during transmission and storage, forming the foundation of data verification mechanisms.

A. Introduction to Hash Functions and Their Properties:

1. **One-Way Function:** Hash functions are designed as one-way functions, meaning it is computationally infeasible to determine the original input from its hash value. This property ensures that sensitive data remains concealed.
2. **Fixed Output Size:** Hash functions produce hash values of a fixed length, regardless of the input size. This consistent output size is crucial for data integrity verification, as any minor input change leads to a significantly different hash value.

B. Common Hashing Algorithms - SHA-256 and SHA-3

1. **SHA-256 (Secure Hash Algorithm 256):** This widely used hashing algorithm generates a 256-bit hash value, ensuring a high degree of collision resistance. SHA-256 is employed in blockchain networks and cryptographic applications due to its reliability and strength against brute-force attacks.
2. **SHA-3 (Secure Hash Algorithm 3):** Introduced as the successor to SHA-256, SHA-3 offers enhanced security and resistance against certain types of attacks. It provides flexibility in terms of output sizes and is considered a promising option for cryptographic applications.

Cryptographic hashing's irreversible nature and ability to produce unique hash values for different inputs make it a cornerstone of data security. It is employed in various contexts, including digital signatures, password hashing, and ensuring the integrity of data blocks within blockchain networks. By providing a secure and efficient method for verifying data authenticity, cryptographic hashing significantly bolsters overall data security.

VII ROLE OF CRYPTOGRAPHIC HASHING IN PERMISSIONED BLOCKCHAINS

Cryptographic hashing forms a crucial linchpin in bolstering the integrity and security of permissioned blockchains. By employing cryptographic hashing techniques, these blockchains ensure data immutability, tamper resistance, and authenticity throughout the network. The process involves transforming raw data into hash values, making it virtually impossible to reverse-engineer the original input from the hash. This cryptographic hash acts as a unique identifier for the data, enabling efficient verification and tamper detection.

A. Illustrating Data Hashing in Permissioned Blockchains:

1. **Data Integrity Assurance:** Prior to appending data to the blockchain, permissioned blockchains subject the input data to a cryptographic hashing algorithm. This results in a hash value that encapsulates the content of the data. Even a small change in the input data would produce a drastically different hash value.
- 2.
3. **Immutable Ledger Entries:** These computed hash values serve as digital fingerprints, securing the content of each transaction or block. Hashing ensures that any alteration in the stored information would lead to a chain reaction of hash value changes throughout the blockchain. This characteristic safeguards against unauthorized modifications, making the blockchain's history immutable.

B. Role of Hash Pointers in Immutable Chains:

1. **Linking Blocks:** Cryptographic hashing enables the chaining of blocks within the blockchain through hash pointers. Each block includes a reference to the hash of the previous block, making a chronological sequence. This linkage guarantees that even a slight modification to a previous block would necessitate the alteration of subsequent blocks, rendering any tampering evident.
2. **Creating an Immutable Chain:** The utilization of hash pointers ensures the establishment of an unbroken chain of blocks, wherein each block is intrinsically linked to its predecessor. The cumulative effect of this linkage is an immutable ledger that provides transparency and data integrity across the permissioned blockchain.

VIII CONCLUSION

The expanding applications of blockchain in technology as well as in other fields of daily life making changes to the storing of the data and tracking them. It relays on decentralized system, with providing security, privacy and transparency to the participants. As the applications are expanding there comes the major issues such as attacking on the blockchain and destroying the nodes. To keep it under the security several major changes and methods are on adaption phase to provide it more security and privacy.

IX REFERENCE

- [1] Blockchain Access Privacy: Challenges and Direction, Aug 2018
- [2] A study of Blockchain -Based Cryptosystems with and without Software Defined Network, Aug 2021
- [3] Privacy preservation in permissionless blockchain, 2021
- [4] Study paper on security aspects of blockchain,
- [5] A Permissioned Blockchain System for secure Multiparty Computation, 202